

3rd International Conference on Nanotechnology Research and Innovation

November 18-21, 2025
University of Aveiro, Portugal
Book of Abstracts

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tema

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3rd International Conference on Nanotechnology Research and Innovation

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Editors

Igor Bdikin
Gil Alberto Batista Gonçalves
Martina Kocijan
Francisco Loureiro
Zhi Jiang

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3rd International Conference on Nanotechnology Research and Innovation, University of Aveiro, Portugal, November 18-21, 2025 (ICNTRI-2025)

ICNTRI-2025 looks for significant Modern Problems of Nanomaterials Research and Innovation, to provide a platform to the global researchers and practitioners from both academia as well as industry to meet and share cutting-edge development in the Nanotechnology science theories, modelling, experiments, industrial implementations.

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Conference Contacts:

info-ICNTRI-2025@icntri.org

Telefone: +351 234 370 830

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2nd Workshop on Challenges and Strategies in Degradation of Organic Contaminants
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W1-O5. Green ZnO photocatalysts for emerging pollutant removal: Powder vs. coating approaches

Szabolcs Bognár^{1,*}, Dušica Jovanović¹, Predrag Putnik², Vesna Despotović¹, Nina Finčur¹,
Sanja Panić³, Branimir Bajac⁴, Daniela Šojić Merkulov¹

¹University of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

²University North, Trg Dr. Žarka Dolinara 1, 48000 Koprivnica, Croatia

³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

⁴Institute BioSense, Dr Zorana Đinđića 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

* Telephone: +381 21 485 2752, E-mail: sabolc.bognar@dh.uns.ac.rs

Advanced oxidation processes, particularly heterogeneous photocatalysis, have gained attention as promising technologies for the degradation of persistent organic micropollutants that are resistant to conventional water treatment methods. The aim of this study was to evaluate the efficiency of eco-inspired ZnO photocatalysts, prepared from green tea (GTE) – and banana peel extracts (BPE), in both powder and coating forms, for the removal of emerging pollutants (pesticide tembotrione – TEM and synthetic hormone 17 α -ethinylestradiol – EE2) from water, under various experimental conditions (catalyst loading, initial pH, water matrix) using simulated solar irradiation. High-performance liquid chromatography with diode array and fluorescence detectors was employed to monitor the degradation kinetics of the target compounds. Additionally, the newly prepared materials were characterized using advanced techniques (e.g. XRD, SEM). The results demonstrated significant photocatalytic activity of the new ZnO materials, with degradation efficiencies reaching 96% for TEM (ZnO GTE) and 83% for EE2 (ZnO BPE), after 60 min of irradiation.

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